

Possible Antiamoebic Agents. Part XV. Compounds Based on the Partial Structure of Aureomycin

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5,5'-Substituted-3-aceto-2,2'-dihydroxybenzophenones, based on the partial structure of aureomycin, have been synthesised with a view to testing their antiamoebic activity.

In recent years the antibiotics, Aureomycin (Ia) and Terramycin (Ib), are being effectively used in the treatment of amoebiasis. Their cure rate is as high as 70% (McVay *et al.*, *Science*, 1949, **109**, 590). The chemistry of these antibiotics has been elucidated by Woodward *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4976) and reviewed by Johnson (*Sci. Progress*, 1953, **41**, 443). These have a common ring system designated as "Tetracycline" (I).

The activity of these compounds is attributed to the presence of chelating -OH and -CO groups in the molecule (Albert *et al.*, *Med. J. Aust.*, 1944, **31**, 245; *Brit. J. Exp. Path.*, 1947, **28**, 69).

In the present investigation 5,5'-substituted-3-aceto-2,2'-dihydroxybenzophenones (II) having two adjacent -CO and -OH groups, as in Aureomycin, have been synthesised with a view to studying the effect of chelation on antiamoebic activity.

The desired compounds were prepared in good yields by the Fries migration of the esters obtained from 5-substituted-2-hydroxyacetophenones with 5-substituted-2-methoxybenzoyl chlorides.

The ketonic esters as well as diketones were characterised through their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones (Tables I and II).

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Methoxybenzoic acid was prepared by Dippy (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1492) by alkaline KMnO_4 oxidation of the corresponding aldehyde, but the yields were not mentioned.

It has now been prepared by a modified method as follows:

2-Methoxybenzaldehyde (10 g.) (obtained by the method of Shoesmith and Connor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2231) was oxidised with 10% aqueous KMnO_4 (125 c.c.) in hot acetone (50 c.c.) solution; acetone was distilled and the remaining solution concentrated and then acidified with HCl. The precipitated acid (yield 10 g.) was recrystallised from water, m.p. 101° (Dippy, *loc. cit.*, reported m.p. 101.5°).

The above acid (6 g.) was converted to its acid chloride according to Marsh (*ibid.*, 1925, 1635), b.p. $120-25^\circ/10\text{mm}$, yield 6g.

5-Chloro-2-methoxybenzoic Acid.—Since it was found difficult to obtain the acid in a pure state by the method of Peratoner (*Gazzetta*, 1898, **28**, 211), it was prepared as follows:

5-Chloro-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (15 g.) (prepared according to Durrans, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 1426) was methylated with methyl sulphate in 10% KOH, yielding methoxybenzaldehyde (8 g.), m.p. 82° (Buu-Hoi, *Compt. rend.*, 1945, **221**, 202, reported m.p. 81°). This aldehyde (10 g.) was oxidised with 10% aqueous KMnO_4 (120 c.c.) in hot acetone (50 c.c.) solution, and the resulting 5-chloro-2-methoxybenzoic acid was isolated and recrystallised from water, yield 10 g., m.p. $82-82.5^\circ$ (Peratoner, *loc. cit.*, reported m.p. $81-82^\circ$).

The acid chloride of the above substance (5 g.) was prepared by the action of thionyl chloride (6 c.c.) and heating on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ an hour, removing the excess of the latter *in vacuo*, and recrystallising the solid acid chloride, thus obtained, from dry benzene, yield 4.5g., m.p. $62.62.5^\circ$ (% Cl found, 34.21; calc., 34.63).

5-Methyl-2-methoxybenzoic Acid.—Mauthner (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1921, **103**, 295) prepared it by methylation of 5-methyl-2-hydroxybenzoic acid, but the same difficulty in obtaining the pure acid arose. It was prepared by the following method.

5-Methyl-2-methoxybenzaldehyde (10 g.) (prepared by the Gattermann reaction, as modified by Adams and Levine, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 1521) was oxidised with 5% aqueous KMnO_4 (220 c.c.) in acetone (50 c.c.) solution at $30-40^\circ$ to yield 5-methyl-2-methoxybenzoic acid, which was crystallised from hot water, yield 9 g., m.p. $66-67^\circ$ (Mauthner, *loc. cit.*, reported m.p. 66°).

This acid was converted to its acid chloride according to Mauthner (*loc. cit.*), b.p. $140-42^\circ/10\text{ mm}$, yield 80%.

2,5-Dimethoxybenzoic Acid.—Kauffmann (*Annalen*, 1905, **344**, 73) obtained it by alkaline KMnO_4 oxidation of 2,5 dimethoxygentisic aldehyde. The present authors obtained it by oxidising the same with aqueous KMnO_4 as follows:

2,5-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde (10 g.) (prepared by the modified Gatterman reaction; cf. Gulland and Viridan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1481) was oxidised with 10% aqueous KMnO_4 (120 c.c.) in hot acetone (50c.c.) solution. Isolated as usual and recrystallised from hot water, it afforded the above acid; yield 10.2 g., m.p. 76° (Kauffmann, *loc. cit.*, reported m.p. 76°).

This acid was converted to its acid chloride in 90% yield with SOCl_2 as usual; b.p. $160-62^\circ/12\text{ mm}$ (Mauthner, *loc. cit.*, reported b.p. $163-64^\circ/15\text{ mm}$).

5-Substituted-2-hydroxyacetophenones were obtained by first acetylating the appropriate *p*-substituted phenols with acetic anhydride (Chattaway, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2495) and then the ester was rearranged with anhydrous AlCl_3 (Fries migration). The following substituted acetophenones were thus obtained:

5-Chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone, yield 100%, m.p. 53-54° (Wittig, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 90, reported m.p. 53.5-54.5°); 5-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone, yield 90% m.p. 50° (Wittig, *loc. cit.*, reported m.p. 45-46°; Rosenmund and Schnurr, *Annalen*, 1927, 480, 83, reported m.p. 50°); 5-methyl-2-hydroxypropiofenone, yield 80%; b.p. 160°/30 mm (Auwers, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 7319, reported b.p. 123-24°/11 mm); 5-methoxy-2-hydroxyacetophenone, by the method of Kostanecki and Lampe (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 774), in 25% yield, m.p. 52°.

4,5'-Substituted-2-acetophenyl 2'-methoxybenzoates were prepared from the appropriate substituted hydroxyacetophenone (0.1*M*), anhydrous benzene (25 c.c.) and magnesium ribbon (1 g.). The appropriate acid chloride (2 methoxy-, 2,5-dimethoxy-, 5-chloro-2-methoxy- or 5-methyl-2-methoxy-benzoyl chloride) (0.1*M*) was then added gradually and the mixture refluxed on a water bath (under CaCl_2 guard tube) for 4 to 5 hours. Benzene was removed under reduced pressure and the residue taken up in ether, washed with 1% NaOH , then with water, dried on anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , and isolated as usual. The m.p. or b.p., yield, their 2,4 dinitrophenyl hydrazones, and their analysis are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	4,5'-Substituted-2-acetophenyl 2'-methoxybenzoate.	B.P. or M.P.	Yield.	2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone.		
				M.P.	% Nitrogen. Found.	Calc.
1.	4-Methoxy	140°/14mm	65%	158°	11.84	11.66
2.	4-Methyl-2-propio	135°/14mm	65	116°	11.82	11.72
3.	4,5'Dichloro	96-97°	66	182-83°	10.86	10.46
4.	4-Methyl-5'-chloro	98°	67	142°	11.42	11.23
5.	4-Chloro-5'-methyl	78°	60	112°	11.41	11.23
6.	4,5'-Dimethyl	75°	62	130°	11.83	11.72
7.	4-Chloro-5'-methoxy	105°	65	210°	10.86	10.79
8.	4-Methyl-5'-methoxy	99°	65	225°	11.42	11.33

Migration of 4,5'-Substituted-2-acetophenyl 2-Methoxybenzoates.—The ester (1*M*) was intimately mixed in a r.b. flask with AlCl_3 (2 to 5*M*, anhyd.). The reaction mixture was then heated in an oil bath at 120° to 160° (Table II) for about 4 hours. The contents were decomposed with 10% ice-cold HCl , taken in ether, washed with 5% NaHCO_3 solution, and then with water. It was dried on anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and isolated in the usual way. The solid hydroxyketones were recrystallised from dry benzene. These were characterised through their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones. During migration, demethylation of the methoxy groups also took place, thus liberating the free hydroxy group.

The physical data, yield, mols. of AlCl_3 used to migrate the corresponding ester, temperature of migration of ester, and analysis of the bis-2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones of the hydroxydiketones are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	5,5'-Substituted-3-aceto- 2,2'-dihydroxy- benzophenone.	B.P. or M.P.	Yield.	Mols. of AlCl ₃ used.	Temp.	Bis-2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone	
						M.P.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.
1.	5-Hydroxy	130°/14mm	50%	3.3	120-30°	230°	17.85 17.72
2.	5-Methyl-3-propio	140°/14mm	50	2.2	120-30°	264°	17.51 17.39
3.	5,5'-Dichloro	156-57°	65	3.3	120-30°	262°	16.48 16.35
4.	5-Methyl-5'-chloro	169°	63	3.3	120-30°	252°	16.98 16.85
5.	5-Chloro-5'-methyl	148°	55	3.3	120-30°	211°	16.97 17.55
6.	5,5'-Dimethyl	146°	56	3.3	120-30°	205°	17.51 17.55
7.	5-Chloro-5'-hydroxy	171°	62	5.5	130-40°4hr. 140-60°1hr.	267°	16.90 16.80
8.	5-Methyl-5'-hydroxy	182°	65	5.5	„	250°	17.48 17.33

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